

Stress tolerance— adverse soils

Promising salt-tolerant F₁ anther culture derivatives (ACDs)

R. K. Singh and B. Mishra, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, India; and D. Senadhira, IRRRI

We evaluated 15 selected ACDs developed at IRRRI (IR51500-AC-17, IR51491-AC-1, IR51491-AC-5, IR51491-AC-6, IR51491-AC-7, IR51485-AC-2, IR51485-AC-3, IR51485-AC-4, AC6533-3, AC6533-4, AC6534-1, AC6534-3, AC6534-4, AC6549, AC6554-2) and tolerant check variety CSR10 for salt tolerance.

Field trials were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications at two sites with different salt stress levels. Gudha had a pH₂ of 10.32 and Mundlana had a pH₂ of 8.23-9.45 and ECe 3.88-10.74 dS/m. Chemical amendments were not applied to the soil.

Forty-day-old seedlings (raised in better soils) were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing. Three doses of N (150 kg/ha total) and one basal dose of Zn (5.75 kg/ha) were applied.

ACDs differed significantly in 50% flowering, plant height, tillers/plant, and productivity (see table). Many derivatives

ANOVA and promising entries of F₁ ACDs.

Promising entry	Days to flowering	Plant height (m)	Panicle bearing tillers (no./plant)	Yield (kg/3 m ²)
<i>Gudha</i>				
AC6533-3	135.0	0.57	7.3	0.446
AC6549	135.7	0.66	6.0	0.270
AC6534-1	133.0	0.73	6.3	0.266
CSR10	103.7	0.57	9.6	0.453
<i>Mundlana</i>				
AC6534-1	115.3	1.02	11.3	1.707
AC6534-4	117.0	0.97	10.3	1.590
IR1500-AC-17	125.3	0.99	12.3	1.420
CSR10	98.7	0.66	11.6	1.413
<i>Average</i>				
AC6534-1	124.2	0.88	8.8	0.986
AC6534-4	125.7	0.85	8.6	0.911
IR1500-AC-17	132.7	0.79	11.1	0.727
CSR10	101.2	0.62	10.6	0.933

SV	DF	MS ^a			
		Days to flowering	Plant height (m)	Panicle bearing tillers (no./plant)	Yield (kg/3 m ²)
Replications within locations	4	11.9	0.036	4.11	0.065
Genotypes (g)	15	500.6*	0.048*	15.20*	0.536*
Locations(1)	1	2175.0*	4.472*	201.30*	8.239*
g × 1	15	57.6*	0.031*	3.70	0.463*
Residual error	60	3.9	0.006	3.60	0.049
LSD					
g		1.9	0.085	1.84	0.214
1		0.7	0.030	0.65	0.075
g × 1		2.7	0.120	—	0.303

^a * = significant at p = 0.05.

exhibited salt tolerance at par with that of CSR 10.

Delayed flowering and maturity of ACDs were the most undesirable traits compared with the early heading and

maturity of check CSR10. We selected AC6534-1 and AC6534-4 as promising lines for our breeding strategies to enhance the salt-affected soil productivity. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Performance of Basmati rices in Rajasthan

R. S. Tripathi and R. Pandya, Agriculture Research Station, Banswara 327001, India

Traditional Basmati rices remain popular in Banswara although they yield poorly and are prone to lodging.

We conducted trials for Basmati rices from 1988 to 1990. Mahi Sugandha, a semidwarf, photoperiod-insensitive variety with basmati-type grains, yielded the most at 5.6 t/ha. Basmati 370 averaged 3.7 t/ha and Kali Kamod, a

popular variety with short, slender grain and strong aroma, 3.5 t/ha (Table 1). Mahi Sugandha significantly

outyielded other varieties, including Basmati 370, in All India Coordinated Trials during kharif 1990. Mahi Sugandha

Table 1. Mean performance of Basmati cultures in Rajasthan, India, 1988-90.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	% increase over Basmati 370	Days to flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)
Mahi Sugandha	5.6	50.6	102	92	489	31.7
IET8580	4.9	30.9	98	84	385	25.0
IET8581	4.3	15.1	99	74	455	20.7
IET8365	3.5	—	100	91	450	24.7
IET10366	3.4	—	99	111	356	27.0
IET10651	3.5	—	121	102	210	23.5
Kali Kamod (c)	3.5	—	105	118	275	21.6
Basmati 370 (c)	3.7	—	107	125	280	27.2

Table 2. Grain quality character of Mahi Sugandha and Basmati 370.

Character	Mahi Sugandha	Basmati 370
Hulling (%)	79.9	79.0
Milling (%)	69.4	64.5
Head rice recovery (%)	50.2	39.2
L/B ratio	3.34	3.48
Classification	Long, slender	Long, slender
Grain length (mm)	5.7	6.2
Length of cooked rice (mm)	10.2	10.8
Kernel color	White	White
Kernel elongation ratio	1.8	1.6
Water uptake	355	300
Volume expansion	2.0	3.2
Alkali value	6.0	5.0
Amylose (%)	27.0	22.3
Test weight (g)	20.5	21.2
Aroma	Strong	Strong
Abdominal white	Absent	Occasionally present

yielded 57.8% more than Basmati 370, which averaged 3.0 t/ha at four locations.

Mahi Sugandha came from BK79/Basmati 370. It matures in 130-135 d from seed and possesses ideal plant type with upright leaves, synchronized tillering, and late leaf senescence. Panicles are fully exerted and compact. They have long, slender, straw-colored grains that are free from abdominal white and strongly scented like Basmati 370 (Table 2). □

Ptb 45 (Matta Triveni), a promising rice variety for dry season in Kerala, India

I. Johnkutty and P. B. Mathews, AICARP-ECF Unit, Kerala Agricultural University, Mannuthy 680651, Thrissur, Kerala, India

Farmers in Kerala prefer high-yielding, short-duration rice varieties for the dry season (Dec/Jan to Apr/May) to allow for timely planting of the succeeding monsoon crop. Annapoorna (90-100 d) has been the most popular variety cultivated.

A short-duration (100 d) rice variety Ptb 45 (Matta Triveni) was recently released by the Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala. The pureline

Grain yield at different locations in 1988 and 1989 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)						
	1988			1989			
	Kodakara	Annamanada	Pananchery	Overall	Annamanada	Pananchery	Overall
Matta Triveni	3.4	4.7	3.2	3.8	3.7	3.5	3.6
Annapoorna	2.1	4.1	2.8	3.0	3.2	2.8	3.0
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.2		0.3	0.2	

selection from Triveni (a white bran variety) is semital with long, compact, and exerted panicles and red, medium-bold grains.

Ptb 45 was compared with Annapoorna under transplanted conditions in different irrigated farming situations in Kerala's central region during DS 1988 and 1989.

Matta Triveni consistently outyielded Annapoorna at all locations in both years (see table). Matta Triveni averaged 3.7 t grain/ha compared with 3 t/ha for Annapoorna.

Although the variety is reported to be susceptible to blast and sheath blight, incidence was less in Matta Triveni than in Annapoorna in the trials. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

BR319-1-HR38 and IR74 released as *gogorancah* varieties in Indonesia

O. Suherman, Sriwidodo, Djafar Baco, and S. Andyantoro, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), P.O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia

Gogorancah is a direct seeded rice culture for dryland conditions that also are flooded by maximum tillering stage. It was developed in rainfed areas using early-maturing lowland rice varieties, such as IR36 and Cisokan.

We conducted yield trials laid out in randomized complete block design with

Table 1. Yield performance of Cenranae (BR319-1-HR38) and IR74 on gogorancah culture. MORIF, Indonesia.

Trials	Grain yield (t/ha)				Cenranae increase (%) over		IR74 increase (%) over	
	Cenranae	IR74	GH-GRM-7	IR21178-39-PI	Cisokan	Cikapundung	Cisokan	Cikapundung
MORIF farm research (1986-89)	6.0	6.0	5.4	4.7	20	22	16	18
Multilocation trials (1987-89)	4.7	4.1	4.2	3.3	38	51	21	32
Adaptive research trial at Sidondo, Central Sulawesi (1988-89)	5.2	4.3	4.1	4.2	44	49	19	23
Adaptive research trial at East Nusatenggara (1988-89)	4.1	4.2	4.2	4.2	24	21	27	23
Adaptive research trial at Wawotobi, Southeast Sulawesi (1988-89)	5.3	4.7	4.7	4.4	23	26	9	12